

Provisioning of Time-Sensitive and non-Time-Sensitive Flows with Assured Performance

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Abstract—Time-Sensitive Networking (TSN) standards provide scheduling and traffic shaping mechanisms to ensure the coexistence of Time-Sensitive (TS) and non-TS traffic classes on the same network infrastructure. Nonetheless, much effort is still needed on the operation of such TSN capable network infrastructure to ensure that the required performance of the different flows, defined in terms of key performance indicators, can be met once the flows are deployed in the network. In this paper, we focus on such aspects and propose a solution involving network-wide scheduling for TS flows, as well as performance estimation for non-TS flows. Specifically, a control plane architecture especially designed for provisioning TS and non-TS flows is proposed. The architecture integrates: *i*) a *TS Flow Scheduler Planner* for defining the scheduling of requested TS flows along a path so as to meet their required performance; and *ii*) a *Network Digital Twin* to estimate the performance of requested and already established non-TS flows. Differently from standardized time-aware schedulers, per-TS flow queues are assumed so as to guarantee minimal jitter. Efficient algorithms are proposed so the provisioning of flows can be carried out with high accuracy and short time. Simulation results for heterogeneous scenarios demonstrate the feasibility and efficiency of the proposed control plane architecture, as well as point out the limitations of current time-synchronization mechanisms when high-speed interfaces are considered.

Index Terms—Time-Sensitive Networking; Network Operation; Time-aware scheduling; Network Digital Twin.

I. INTRODUCTION

TIME-Sensitive Networking (TSN) consists of a set of standards defined by the IEEE 802.1 working group [1], which includes the 802.1Qbv time-aware scheduler (TAS) [2]. TSN uses a time-synchronization mechanism, such as the Precision Time Protocol version 2 (PTPv2) [3], to ensure that all nodes in the TSN infrastructure share a common time reference. TAS works according to a predefined and static Gate Control List (GCL) of fixed length that specifies when queues are in open and closed states. The scheduler needs to be defined in a way that *Time-Sensitive (TS) flows* meet the required Quality of Service (QoS) defined in terms of Key Performance Indicators (KPI), such as end-to-end (e2e) delay and delay variation (jitter). The surveys in [4], [5] overview standards and research efforts related to TSN.

To simplify its computation, the GCL can be defined considering a set of time slots to form a *superframe* (SF) that repeats over time. Although each time slot can be assigned to several TS flows, that would make that the traffic of one TS flow impact the performance of others, which impacts determinism. In addition, the cyclic scheduling might introduce jitter to TS flows with a periodicity shorter than the SF, which is inapplicable to isochronous flows that require zero jitter [10]. Thus, the allocation of such time slots needs to be faced from a *network perspective* to ensure e2e performance. In addition, the TSN infrastructure might require connectivity with other non-TS capable nodes, which are used for supporting non-TS flows.

In this work, we target a realistic *Heterogeneous TSN networking* scenario, where time slots are assigned to a single TS flow and traffic flows of multiple classes can coexist. Individual service provisioning requests arrive sequentially, where each request might consist of an heterogenous set of TS and non-TS flows. Examples of application requiring such heterogenous set of flows include Industrial Automated Guided Vehicles (AGV) [11]. Since time slots are reserved for TS flows, requests need to consider the current resource availability in the network. A *TS Flow Scheduler Planner* (TS FSP) is in charge of finding a feasible scheduling for TS flows meeting the required QoS. Even though scheduling is found, the impact on the QoS of already established non-TS flows should be checked to finally accept or reject the request. In consequence, we use a *Network Digital Twin* (NDT) for estimating the QoS of traffic flows near-real-time.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section II reviews the state-of-the-art related to TS flow scheduling and NDT for QoS estimation, especially for heterogeneous TSN networking, and details the contributions of our work. Section III proposes a control plane architecture for heterogenous TSN networks that includes TS-FSP and NDT systems. A provisioning algorithm for TS and non-TS flows that takes advantage of the architecture is also presented. Section IV focuses on the TS-FSP problem that finds time allocations for requested TSN flows and Section V centers on the NDT used during provisioning to estimate the KPIs of non-TS flows. Section VI evaluates the performance of the proposed provisioning algorithm by simulation. Finally, Section

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VII draws the main conclusions of our work.

II. RELATED WORK AND CONTRIBUTIONS

Some previous works have proposed solutions for scheduling a set of flows. The authors in [7] addressed the computation of deterministic schedules on IEEE 802.1Qbv-compliant multi-hop switched networks assuming *full-duplex* physical links. They considered a frame isolation constraint to ensure that streams use always the same time slots. More recently, the authors in [8] studied the combinability of multiple TS flows, while leaving resources available for non-TS flows. They proposed a deterministic network scheduling for TS flows, as a planning problem to be solved beforehand for all the flows simultaneously. Once resources are allocated to TS flows, packet schedulers assign resources to *non-TS flows* dynamically. Because TS flows can arrive sequentially to the network, the authors in [9] proposed a Machine Learning approach to dynamically schedule any incoming flow. The online algorithm was complemented with an Integer Linear Programming (ILP) model that is triggered to recalculate the entire schedule. The authors in [10] proposed a TS network architecture based on Software-Defined Networking (SDN) for serving TS requests that arrive sequentially. They provided real-time guarantees for time-triggered flows by scheduling their transmissions on the network edge only by exploiting the global view of the SDN control plane. They assumed *zero queuing delay* for TSN traffic, i.e., whenever packets belonging to a TS flow arrive at a switch, the output ports must be free or non-TS traffic be pre-empted. By (almost) eliminating the queuing delay in the network, TS packets can be delivered to their destinations as early as possible.

Heterogeneous TSN networking was recently studied by the authors in [12], which proposed a scheduling paradigm involving a network calculus worst-case interference analysis within the scheduling step. The scenario is similar in our work, as we also consider a heterogenous network infrastructure, where TS flows are exclusively supported through TSN-capable devices, which share a common clock reference, whereas non-TSN-capable devices support non-TS traffic only. However, we rely on the TS FSP for the scheduling of TS flows along a given path. Such scheduling together with the exclusive time slot reservation guarantees the performance of TS flows in terms of delay and jitter. In addition, we rely on the NDT to estimate the performance of non-TS flows with multiple priorities, that use the time slots that remain free after the allocation for the TS flows and for the non-TS flows both higher priorities.

The use of an NDT has been shown to be of paramount importance for estimating the performance of traffic flows near-real-time [13]-[14]. In those works, both service traffic and queues behavior in packet nodes were modeled. Extensions proposed in [15] consider time awareness, thus supporting IEEE 802.1Qbv. Note that such architecture can be seen as an extension of the Intent-based Networking paradigm [16], where the TS FSP specializes on TS flows whereas the NDT specializes on non-TS ones. In addition, both TS FSP and NDT consider not only full-duplex links, but also *half-duplex* one, e.g., WiFi, which are needed to provide wireless access to end devices [17]. Another issue that needs to be considered is the feasible width of the time slots. The increasing speed of network interfaces, with tens or hundreds of Gb/s, makes the slot width to be limited by the precision of the synchronization protocol used; e.g., PTPv2 has precision of tens of ns [18], which entails some capacity wasting that needs to be analyzed.

The overall methodology, based on the above elements, was firstly presented in [19], showing how they need to coordinate to operate a TS infrastructure that guarantees performance while maximizing resource utilization. In brief, a control plane based on the SDN paradigm includes both a TS FSP and an NDT working under the assumption of the worst-case scenario, e.g., the minimum Modulation and Coding Scheme (MCS) in WiFi interfaces, so as the performance of the flows is guaranteed. However, the data plane cannot be operated under the worst-case scenario as that would result in a poor resource utilization. In consequence, the work in [19] provided the additional mechanisms to be implemented in the local packet schedulers managing the GCL of network interfaces to maximize resource utilization and improve the performance of non-TS flows. In this work, we concentrate on the TS FSP and NDT and provide mathematical formulae and algorithmic solutions.

Finally, limited computation time, as part of the total time of service provisioning, is an important requirement, and therefore, efficient solving methods for both TS FSP and NDT are needed. Specifically, different solutions can be considered for the NDT, like using simulation network tools (e.g., ns3 [20]), to compute KPIs with high accuracy. However, such approach entails large computation time. Other approaches that are faster than simulation, involve analytics methods, like network calculus [21]. However, such approaches are difficult to apply in heterogenous scenarios, with different types of interfaces [22], traffic profiles, etc. In this respect, in our previous work in [13]-[15], we proposed a methodology named CURSA-SQ to analyze traffic flows in converged fixed-mobile networks and TSN by modelling service traffic and the behavior of the queues in packet nodes. CURSA-SQ enables near real-time traffic analysis (with sub-second resolution) due to its better performance and scalability compared to traditional discrete-event based simulations (e.g., ns-3).

A summary of the limitations identified from the related works together with the contributions of our work is presented in Table 1. Specifically, the contributions are:

- The control plane architecture for heterogenous TSN networks proposed in Section III, together with an algorithm for provisioning TS and non-TS flows from service requests. The control plane includes TS-FSP and the NDT systems that play key roles during provisioning. The assumed queue models for time-aware and non-time-aware devices are also defined.

- The TS-FSP problem that finds time allocations for requested TSN flows is detailed, formally stated as an optimization problem, and modeled as an ILP in Section IV. A heuristic approach is proposed to provide near-optimal solutions in short time, thus fitting the requirements for service provisioning.

Table 1: Summary of Related works and contributions.

Topics	Limitations of Related Works	Contributions
<i>Network Scenario</i>	Multi-hop switched networks with full-duplex physical links [7]. TS and non-TS scenarios faced as a planning problem [8].	Heterogeneous WiFi + Ethernet TSN and non-TS network scenarios with half- and full-duplex links. Control plane architecture and service provisioning algorithm for TS and non-TS flows.
<i>Queueing model</i>	Ports with fixed number of queues and time slots in output interfaces can be assigned to several TS flows [2]. <i>Zero queuing delay</i> [10] to (almost) eliminate the queuing delay.	We assume one queue per-TS flow and time slots are assigned to a single TS flow. TS flows can be queued provided that the committed e2d delay and jitter are met.
<i>TS flow scheduling</i>	Existing approaches are difficult to apply in heterogeneous scenarios [12] and optimal scheduling requires several iterations [9].	TS FSP finds time allocations for requested TSN flows. TS FSP is modelled as an ILP and solved using heuristics algorithms to minimize computation time.
<i>non-TS flow KPI estimation</i>	Simulation tools involve long computation time [20] or are difficult to apply in heterogeneous scenarios [22].	Our NDT extends CURSA-SQ [13]-[15] to estimate the KPIs of non-TS flows for provisioning in heterogeneous network scenarios.

Fig. 1: Heterogeneous TSN network and overview of the proposed architecture

Fig. 2: Illustrative heterogeneous TSN network scenario.

- The NDT used during provisioning to estimate the KPIs of non-TS flows is detailed in Section V. The NDT, based on the CURSA-SQ methodology, emulates a partitioning that includes the nodes and links in the paths of the flows of the service request. Such network partitioning is translated into a queue system and solved in practical times to generate metrics that are used afterwards for KPIs computation.

The discussion is supported by the results presented in Section VI for an illustrative network scenario, where four TS and non-TS network domains are interconnected through a transport network. The results show that the proposed provisioning algorithm for the new TS flows together with the NDT to estimate the KPIs of the new and already existing non-TS flows, provides highly accurate results in the times required for the service provisioning process.

III. TSN ARCHITECTURE AND FLOW PROVISIONING

Fig. 1 presents the heterogeneous TSN network scenario considered in this paper that includes network nodes with and without TSN capabilities. Although the network supports both TS and non-TS packet flows, which are mixed in some of the network devices, TS flows are exclusively supported through TSN-capable devices. An illustrative example is presented in Fig. 2 that includes two TSN-capable WiFi access points (AP), three TSN Ethernet switches, and two non-TSN capable packet routers. The network connects two robotic arms, two servers, and a number of users and devices. Two TS flows (denoted TS-1 and TS-2) are routed through a path connecting the robotic arms to their controller running in Server A. Additionally, one of the robotic arms generates a video flow that requires some QoS performance (QoS-1). The users and other devices are connected to Server B, and different priorities of traffic are considered, from low priority, i.e., best effort (BE), to high priority.

Fig. 3: Assumed queue model for time-aware (a) and non-time-aware (b) devices.

Fig. 3a illustrates the queue model assumed for TSN capable devices, which is different from the one defined in [2] since TS flows have dedicated queues and servers; the rest of the classes have a single priority server with per-priority queues as in [2]. Each of these servers (gates in [2]) are *time-aware* governed by their own scheduler $\mu_{(\cdot)}(t)$. The interface is represented by a single server that is fed by a queue and works at the maximum speed of the interface (μ). Note that the queue model for non-TSN capable devices (Fig. 3b) includes a single no time-aware server with constant service rate μ .

To control such a heterogeneous network, we rely on SDN controllers with TSN capabilities (denoted TSN controller), as well as without TSN capabilities. Controllers use a south-bound interface to program the different network devices under their control. A TSN Connectivity Manager (CM) provides e2e control and includes, among other components: *i*) a *Path computation element* (PCE) implementing algorithms with different policies that are applied as a function of the type of flow that needs to be provisioned; *ii*) a TS-FSP in charge of producing worst-case scheduling for the TS flows to be deployed in the network; and *iii*) an NDT that evaluates relevant KPIs of non-TS flows before new (TS or non-TS) flows are deployed. The NDT considers non-TS flows with different priorities. All flows are served on a particular path defined for each flow. However, TS flows have specific resources reserved along their path, whereas non-TS ones use the remaining resources, which are assigned by their priority (see queue models in Fig. 3).

When a new *service request* arrives at the TSN CM, a provisioning process is followed, that includes path computation, scheduling planning (in the case that the request includes some new TS flow), and performance evaluation. If the service request is accepted, the TSN CM uses SDN and TSN controllers' north-bound interfaces to send them precise instructions for the new flows. Specifically, in the case of TS flows, the TSN CM sends to the TSN controllers the computed network scheduling plan together with a point in time when that plan needs to be implemented. The TSN controllers will subsequently provide that plan and time to the packet schedulers running in the TSN-capable nodes that transform into a GCL. In the case of non-TS flows, both TSN and SDN controllers might be involved in the provisioning process.

Let us overview the provisioning process of TS and non-TS flows in the TSN CM. The process starts when a new service request arrives at the TSN CM and ends with that request being accepted or rejected. The general algorithm running in the TSN CM for flow provisioning is presented in Fig. 4. Note that a service request might involve several flow requests that have to be all accepted for the service request to be accepted. Therefore, the flow provisioning has to be executed sequentially for all the flows involved in the service request, grouped by priority in the case of non-TS flows, and the resources selected for previous flows should be reserved to compute the resources and KPIs of subsequent flows.

The algorithm receives the characteristics of the flow(s), including the end-points, class of service (e.g., TS, or priority) KPI requirements, if any, traffic profile including periodicity in the case of a TS flow, and others (step 1 in Fig. 4). The algorithm follows a different procedure for TS and non-TS flows (2). In the case of TS flows, k -shortest paths (SP) are computed on a subgraph that includes the end-points of the flow and nodes with TSN capabilities (3). Next, the TS-FSP module selects a SP and finds a scheduling plan for the new TS flow so as to meet the requirements (4). If no scheduling plan is found, the next SP is selected (5) and the loop continues until no more SPs are left, which means that no resources are available for the new TS flow request, and the request is rejected (6). If a scheduling plan is found (7), the NDT is called to estimate the performance of the non-TS flows already being served as if the TS flow were setup (8). This is a crucial step, as the new TS flow will be assigned resources in detriment of non-TS flows and that could impact their KPIs. In case the performance of QoS committed flows can be guaranteed, the flow request is accepted (9). Otherwise, the algorithm checks whether reducing the committed performance of the impacted flows is possible (10). On the contrary, the next SP is selected (11) until a solution is found or the request is finally rejected (12). Non-TS flows provisioning follows a similar procedure except for the scheduling plan and the way paths are computed.

Once the provisioning algorithm finishes, the scheduling is applied to the involved nodes in an orchestrated manner. To that end, a point in time in the future is selected at which all devices will update the schedule.

Fig. 4: Provisioning algorithm for TS and non-TS Flows.

IV. TS FLOW SCHEDULING PLANNER (TS-FSP)

This section first introduces the TS-FSP problem, which is then formally stated as an optimization problem and modelled as an ILP problem. In view of the short times available for solving the TS-FSP problem during provisioning phase, heuristic algorithms are proposed.

A. TS-FSP overview

TS-FSP is executed for a TS flow request r to be served on a computed path with the objective of reserving resources along that path to support the TS flow. The request is defined by path $E(r)$, i.e., an ordered list of undirected links, the traffic characteristics, i.e., the number of bits b to be transmitted every period and the periodicity P , the delay to be ensured δ and the maximum jitter v . The resources to be allocated for the TS flow are a set of time windows, with duration specific for each link along the defined path. The resource allocation repeats for the given periodicity. In the case that the required resources cannot be reserved for the TS flow request, the request is blocked. The transmission on any link e in the network is organized in terms of a SF, which consists of a set of time slots in the range $[1..T_e]$, each of duration τ_e , where each time slot t can be allocated to only one TS flow. To that end, a resource allocation *window* (w_e) with a number of contiguous time slots to be allocated in every link e is computed for the request. Note that the aggregated capacity of each w_e considers the traffic specifics of the request, defined by b , the capacity of time slots, as well as some band guard.

Fig. 5: Illustrative example of NSF' after TS-2 flow request.

Fig. 6: Examples of scheduling in two consecutive links.

(a) zero queuing delay																					Flow	Delay	Jitter			
Link/Slot	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	TS-1	TS-2	TS-3	TS-4	TS-5	
e1		TS-1	TS-2						TS-3	TS-4						TS-5					TS-1	4	0	TS-2	8	0
e2			TS-1	TS-2					TS-3			TS-4					TS-5				TS-3	4	0	TS-4	8	0
e3				TS-1			TS-2						TS-3		TS-4				TS-5		TS-4	8	0	TS-5	4	0
e4					TS-1			TS-2				TS-3				TS-4				TS-5	TS-5	4	0			
e5						TS-1				TS-2		TS-3					TS-4			TS-5						

(b) per-TS Queues																					Flow	Delay	Jitter			
Link/Slot	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	TS-1	TS-2	TS-3	TS-4	TS-5	
e1	TS-1	TS-2		TS-3	TS-4				TS-5												TS-1	4	0	TS-2	8	0
e2			TS-1	TS-2		TS-3	TS-4			TS-5											TS-3	8	0	TS-4	8	0
e3				TS-1			TS-2		TS-3	TS-4					TS-5						TS-5	8	0			
e4					TS-1			TS-2			TS-3	TS-4			TS-5											
e5						TS-1				TS-2		TS-3	TS-4		TS-5											

Fig. 7: Illustrative scheduling under zero queuing delay (a) and per-TS queues (b).

Fig. 5 illustrates the network SF' (NSF) for a simplified scenario based on Fig. 2, where only the relevant links for the TS-1 (existing) and TS-2 (request) flows are depicted. In this example, no transmission delay is considered and all the interfaces are of the same speed B . In consequence, time slots are of the same duration for every link. Time-related values are expressed in time units (tu), so the duration of NSF is $T=20tu$ and that of every time slot is 1 tu. TS-1 is defined as: $\{E_{TS-1}=[AP2-WiFi-UL, AP2-SW1, SW-SW2, SW2-SW3, SW3-SA], T_{TS-1}=1, P_{TS-1}=4, \delta_{TS-1}=6, v_{TS-1}=2\}$, and TS-2 is defined as: $\{E_{TS-2}=[AP1-WiFi-UL, AP1-SW1, SW-SW2, SW2-SW3, SW3-SA], T_{TS-2}=2, P_{TS-2}=10, \delta_{TS-2}=12, v_{TS-2}=2\}$. Since links AP1-WiFi-UL and AP2-WiFi-UL are half-duplex (uplink, UL), some of the time slots are not available as they are reserved for the downlink (DL) direction.

Under such NSF', the delay of flow TS-1 is 6 for every period, so its jitter is 0. We assume that the first bits of the TS flow are available at the start of the SF and after every period. Therefore, the delay for every period of a flow can be easily computed by subtracting the starting time of the window of the last allocation in the path to the time slot where the data is available. In the case of flow TS-2, the delay is 11 and 9 for the first and the second periods, respectively, which represents a jitter of 2. In consequence, the TS-2 flow request is accepted.

In the example in Fig. 5, time windows in two consecutive links in the path of the request *overlap*, i.e., bits are started to be transmitted through the output interface before the whole packet has arrived at the input interface in the same node. This means that the nodes should be capable to forward the received bits with minimum buffering, so the delay can be minimized (we call this *express mode*). Note that the express mode can potentially provide lower delay than the *cut-through* mode [26] since the former is based on time slot allocation, i.e., it forwards received bytes to the output interface without waiting for the destination address in the packet header. If such capability is not implemented, packets need to be received completely in the node before they can be transmitted through an output interface, i.e., working in a traditional *store&forward* mode, which introduces additional delay.

Fig. 6 presents an illustrative example of express and store&forward modes in a single node, where e1 is the input interface and e2 is the output interface for a TS flow. In Fig. 6a input and output interfaces are of the same speed, so the express mode can start the transmission of the received data adding only 1 tu of delay, whereas the store&forward mode adds 6 tu. In the example in Fig. 6b, the speed of the input interface is much lower than that of the output interface, so, in the express mode, bits have to wait until just enough arrive to start the transmission. However, 2 tu delay reduction w.r.t. the store&forward mode is observed.

Finally, Fig. 7 shows a comparison between zero queuing delay [10] and the per-TS queues in the output interfaces of time-aware devices (see Fig. 3a), assuming the store&forward mode. Five TS flow requests between the same end-points arrive sequentially and require 1 or 2 time slots. We observe that all the TS flows experience between 4 and 8 tu delay with no jitter under both queuing models. Assuming that data is ready to be transmitted at the beginning of the assigned time window in the first link and that the maximum delay for the respective TS application is over 8 tu, both solutions can provide the requested TS flows. However, because of the heterogeneous time window required by each TS-flow request, time fragmentation can be observed under both queuing models, being particularly relevant in the case of zero queuing delay. However, the ability to queue frames results in a much smaller fragmentation of the superframes, which improves resource utilization. In this example, we observe that no additional TS-requests can be accepted due to resource exhaustion when the zero queuing delay model is used. In contrast, when queues are employed, resources are available to support new TS-flows.

Once computed, the TSN CM uses NSF' to provide the worst-case plan to the scheduling algorithm controlling packet forwarding in the interfaces of the network devices. Before that, every SF'_e needs to be processed, since they might include allocation blocks that repeat periodically. For instance, NSF' in Fig. 5 includes AP1-WiFi and AP2-WiFi interfaces with two and five repetitions, respectively, which are removed to produce the final SF_e to be sent to the related packet scheduler.

B. Problem Statement

The TS-FSP problem can be formally stated follows:

Given:

- The network topology $G(E)$, modelled as a set of *directed* links E . Each link is characterized by: *i*) the speed of the interfaces B_e or, alternatively, the duration of each time slot in that link τ_e . In the case that an interface can offer different speeds (e.g., it is common that wireless interfaces can adapt their modulation format as a function of the quality of the signal of the receiver), the lowest speed is considered. This assumption guarantees the performance of the TS flows even under the worst-case scenario; *ii*) its transmission delay d_e .
- The duration T of the SF. We assume a fixed duration that limits the longest periodicity of the TS flows that can be served. In every link e , a superframe SF_e , in the form of an ordered list of time slots, is defined. Note that the duration of each time slot τ_e can be defined from speed B_e . In addition, each link can be full-duplex or half-duplex, where the former links have time slots available during the whole SF_e duration, whereas the latter links have time slots available only during part of the SF_e duration.
- The current scheduling plan of the network $NSF = \{SF_e, \forall e \in E\}$. Every SF_e defines the allocations of slots to existing TS flows.
- A new TS flow request $r = (E(r), P, b, \delta, v)$. The new request r can be served only if time windows can be reserved along path $E(r)$ with enough capacity for the required number of bits b and the periodicity P_r , so that delay (δ) and jitter (v) constraints are met. The delay is computed for every period and the jitter is computed as the difference between the maximum and minimum delay of the different periods.

Objective: To serve the request and minimize the jitter.

In the case that it is feasible to serve the TS flow request, the new scheduling plan for the network $NSF' = \{SF'_e\}$ is returned.

C. Problem modeling

TS-FSP is modelled as an ILP problem. The used notation is summarized in Table 2. The original parameters introduced in the problem statement are included under the *network* and *flow request* sections in Table 2. To simplify the formulation, some parameters are pre-computed. Finally, decision variables are listed. A short description is included for reference.

Algorithm 1 presents the pseudocode for parameters pre-computation. The number of periods per SF of the request is first computed (line 1). Next, parameters related to the links are defined (lines 2-11). First, the number of time slots and the size of the time window are computed for each link (line 3). Note that twice the size of the SF is considered to allow window allocations after the end of the first SF, thus creating a kind of *circular* structure that needs to be managed in a postprocessing phase (see an example in Fig. 5, where time slot 1 in link SW3-SA is part of the window allocated to TS-2). Then, parameter η is computed to indicate whether the time window for the request can start at every time slot considering the size of the window (lines 4). Next, the first time slot that can be selected for the allocation in the next link in the path is computed (see numerical examples in Fig. 6) (lines 5-11). If the store&forward mode is selected, the slot must be the one that ensures that the complete packet has been received in the node connecting both links (line 7). In the case of the express mode, overlapping is allowed (lines 8-10) and the first slot in e_2 where the window can start is computed. If the effective speed of e_1 is higher or equal than that of e_2 , the first time slot starting in link e_2 after one time slot in e_1 can be selected (line 9), as in Fig. 6. Otherwise, the scheduling of the window in s_2 is scheduled to finish in the next time slot in e_2 after the complete transmission in e_1 (line 10), as in Fig. 6b. In both modes, the delay in e_1 is also considered (line 11). A new link is added in the first position of links in the path (lines 12-14) to represent data availability for each of the periods and it has similar characteristics of the first physical one, with no delay. Finally, the precomputed parameters are returned (line 15).

Table 2: Notation.

<i>Network sets and parameters</i>	
E	set of directed links in the topology; index e .
B_e	speed of the interfaces in link e .
τ_e	duration (in μs) of each time slot in link e .
d_e	transmission delay of link e .
b_e	information bits transmitted every time slot in link e , computed considering the speed of the interfaces and the duration of each time slot in the link.
SF_e	superframe for link e . $SF_e = [s_{et}]$, each component s_{et} is 1 if time slot t is available in the link, i.e., both it is not already allocated to an existing TS flow and it can be used for transmission.
T_e	number of time slots in link e , index t .
NSF	network SF, defined as a set of $SF_e \forall e \in E$.
T	total duration of NSF.
<i>TS flow request, r</i>	
$E(r)$	path defined for the requested TS flow.
P	periodicity of the requested TS flow.
b	bits to be transmitted per period
δ	maximum delay (in μs) to be ensured.
v	maximum jitter (in μs) to be ensured.
<i>mode</i>	{express, store&forward}

<i>Pre-computed parameters</i>	
P_r	number of periods covered in one SF. Note that we assume $P_r \in \mathbb{Z}$.
$E(r)$	A special source link is added representing the application generating data in the local interface. Time windows are forced to be scheduled at the starting of each period.
w_e	size of the time window that needs to be reserved for the requested TS flow in each link $e \in E(r)$.
η_{et}	1 if the time window for the request can start at time t in link e ; 0 otherwise.
σ_e	maximum overlapping (in μs) of window in link $e+1$ w.r.t. that in link e , being $e+1$ the consecutive link to e in path $E(r)$.
<i>Decision Variables</i>	
x_{etp}	binary: equal to 1 if the time window for the flow request starts at timeslot t in period p over link e ; 0 otherwise.
y_p	\mathbb{Z}^+ : maximum number of timeslots of period p .
y_{max}	\mathbb{Z}^+ : bounded maximum number of timeslots for the request.
z	\mathbb{Z}^+ : bounded maximum difference of timeslots for r .

Algorithm 1. Parameter precomputation.

INPUT: *Given sets and parameters, mode*
OUTPUT: *Pre-computed parameters*

```

1:  $P_r \leftarrow T / P$ 
2: for  $e1: 1..|E(r)|$  do
3:    $e1.T \leftarrow 2 * T / e.\tau$ ;  $e1.w \leftarrow \lceil b / e.b \rceil$ 
4:   for  $t: 1..e1.T$  do  $e1.\eta[t] \leftarrow \text{available}(e1.SF, t, e1.w)$ 
5:    $e2 \leftarrow e1 + 1$ 
6:    $last\_e1 \leftarrow e1.w * e1.\tau$ ;  $first\_e2 \leftarrow \lceil last\_e1 / e2.\tau \rceil * e2.\tau$ 
7:   if  $mode = \text{store\&forward}$  then  $s \leftarrow first\_e2$ 
8:   else // express
9:     if  $e1.b / e1.\tau > e2.b / e2.\tau$  then  $s \leftarrow \lceil e1.\tau / e2.\tau \rceil * e2.\tau$ 
10:    else  $s \leftarrow first\_e2 - (e2.w - \lceil e1.b / e2.b \rceil) * e2.\tau$ 
11:    $e1.\sigma \leftarrow \lceil (s + e1.d) / e1.\tau \rceil$ 
12:    $e0 \leftarrow E(r)[1]$ ;  $e0.d \leftarrow 0$ ;  $e0.\sigma \leftarrow 0$ ;  $e0.\eta \leftarrow [0] * e0.T$ 
13:   for  $p: 1..P_r$  do  $e0.\eta[1+(p-1)*P] \leftarrow 1$ 
14:    $E(r).\text{insert}(e0)$ 
15: return  $\langle P_r, E(r) \rangle$ 

```

The ILP formulation for the TS-FSP problem is presented next, where the objective function (1) targets at minimizing the jitter for the TS flow request. Constraints (2)-(5) deal with time windows allocation to guarantee that they are allocated in all the links along the path and for all the periods, and use available slots. Constraint (2) ensures that the time window starts in a time slot t that is available in link e . Constraint (3) assures that every slot t in every link is not selected more than once as starting of the time window for any period. In addition, if time slot t in link e is selected in the first SF, constraint (3) prevents that time slot $t'=t+T_e/2$ or any subsequent timeslot until the size of the window in e is selected (circular SF). Constraint (4) guarantees that a time window is allocated for every period in every link along the route for the requested TS flow. Constraint (5) selects the time window in every link along the path, so the time window in a link starts once enough data (depending on the selected mode) has arrived from the previous link, to be able to convey the data within a window of the specific size for that link. Constraints (6)-(10) compute delay and jitter and guarantee that the required performance is met. Constraint (6) computes the number of time slots observed at the last link in the route since the starting of each period. Variable y_{max} in constraint (7) bounds the maximum of the delays observed in every period and constraint (8) ensures that that bound, now computed as time and considering the delay in the last link, is under the maximum for the TS flow request. Variable z in constraint (9) bounds the maximum difference of the delays observed in every period and constraint (10) ensures that such difference computed as time meets the jitter constraint for the request.

$$\text{(TS-FSP)} \quad \min \quad z \tag{1}$$

subject to:

$$x_{etp} \leq \eta_{et} \quad \forall e: 1..|E(r)|, t: 1..T_e, p: 1..P_r \tag{2}$$

$$\sum_{p: 1..P_r} x_{etp} + \sum_{t': t'_a..t'_b} \sum_{p: 1..P_r} x_{et'p} \leq 1 \tag{3}$$

$$\forall e: 1..|E(r)|, t: 1..T_e/2,$$

$$t'_a = (t + T_e/2), t'_b = \min(t'_a + w_e - 1, T_e)$$

$$\sum_{t: 1..T_e} x_{etp} = 1 \quad \forall e: 1..|E(r)|, p: 1..P_r \tag{4}$$

$$\tau_{e+1} \cdot \sum_{t:1..T_{e+1}} x_{e+1tp} \cdot t \geq \tau_e \cdot \sum_{t:1..T_e} x_{etp} \cdot t + \sigma_e \quad (5)$$

$$\forall e: 1..|E(r)| - 1, p: 1..P_r$$

$$y_p = \sum_{t:1..T_e} (t-1) \cdot x_{etp} - P \cdot (p-1) \quad \begin{array}{l} \forall e: |E(r)| \\ p: 1..P_r \end{array} \quad (6)$$

$$y_{max} \geq y_p \quad \forall p: 1..P_r \quad (7)$$

$$\tau_e \cdot y_{max} + d_e \leq \delta \quad e: |E(r)| \quad (8)$$

$$z \geq y_{p'} - y_p \quad \forall p, p': 1.. \quad (9)$$

$$\tau_e \cdot z \leq v \quad \forall e = |E(r)|, \quad (10)$$

The TS-FSP problem is *NP-hard* since it is based upon the flow-shop scheduling problem, which has been proved to be *NP-hard* [23]. Regarding problem size, the number of variables and constraints are defined in eq. (11)-(12).

$$\#vars = O(|E(r)| \cdot \max_{e \in E(r)} (T_e) \cdot P_r) \quad (11)$$

$$\#consts = O(P_r^2 + |E(r)| \cdot (|E(r)| \cdot P_r + \max_{e \in E(r)} (T_e))) \quad (12)$$

To quantify the size of problem instances, i.e., $\#vars \times \#consts$, let us assume a scenario of a TS flow request with period $P = 1$ ms to be scheduled on a path with 1 link and SF duration $T = 10$ ms. If WiFi interfaces are considered with slot duration $\tau_e = 4$ μ s (1 OFDM symbol with worst MCS) then, the size of the instance would be $\approx 10^9$. Nonetheless, if 10 Gb/s interfaces are considered with slot duration of 1 byte, the size increases to $\approx 10^{16}$. Note that constraint (2) fixes some x_{etp} variables to 0, which greatly reduces the total size of the problem. Still, the time for solving the problem to the optimality might be, in general, too long for TS flow provisioning, even using commercial solvers such as CPLEX [24]. In consequence, a heuristic approach is proposed next.

D. Heuristic algorithm

We have selected a simple greedy constructive followed by a local search approach to find near-optimal solutions to the TS-FSP problem. The greedy algorithm (see the pseudocode in Algorithm 2) receives the details of the TS flow request and returns an initial plan that focuses exclusively on guaranteeing the delay, i.e., it might not be necessarily a feasible solution of the problem as the jitter is not checked. After initializing a vector where the scheduling for each period will be stored (line 1 in Algorithm 2), an iterative procedure is executed for every period (lines 2-9). A structure to store the best candidate time slot allocation for the period is initialized with infinite delay (line 3) and it will be updated any time a better candidate, in terms of delay, is found for the current period. Then, possible allocations starting in the time of the current period until the period that will result in the maximum delay are explored (lines 4-7). The algorithm checks whether a time window can start in the current time slot in the first link of the path (line 5) and an e2e window allocation is found starting from that time slot (line 6). Such candidate allocation is the one with lowest delay starting in the initial time slot. Therefore, the delay of the candidate is checked and if it is better than the current minimum, the candidate is saved as the best found so far for the current period (line 7). Once all the time slots are explored, the best candidate allocation is checked to be under the maximum delay (line 8) and stored in the scheduling for the TS flow (line 9); otherwise, the request is infeasible and it is blocked. Finally, a plan with the lowest delay for each period, together with the resulting jitter is returned (line 10).

Algorithm 3 presents the pseudocode of the findCandidateAllocation() function. This function finds an e2e candidate allocation for a given period starting in a given time slot of the first link in the path. After some initializations (line 1 in Algorithm 3), allocations for the rest of the links are found (lines 2-10). The time slot in the next link is computed from the time slot in the previous link using the durations of their respective time slots and considering the maximum window overlapping (line 3). The possible allocations for the time window are checked and the first available one is selected (lines 4-8). In case that no allocation is possible, a candidate with infinite delay is returned (line 9); otherwise, the allocation is stored (line 10). Finally, the delay of the candidate is computed (line 11) and returned together with some other information (line 12).

The pseudocode of the local search phase is presented in Algorithm 4. The algorithm receives an initial plan from the greedy constructive phase that is not guaranteed to be a solution of the TS-FSP problem because the maximum jitter can be exceeded. The algorithm runs until the jitter of the plan is under the maximum for the TS flow or no solution is found (lines 1-8 in Algorithm 4). To minimize the jitter, the periods with maximum and minimum delay are first selected (line 2). An allocation with delay closer to the period with the maximum delay is selected for the period with the minimum delay, without exceeding the maximum delay allowed (line 3). A new plan is generated by replacing the previous with the new allocation for the period (lines 4-5) and

the resulting jitter is computed (line 6). If the jitter is not improved, the algorithm returns infeasible, otherwise, the new plan is stored and the search continues (line 8). Finally, the obtained solution that meets delay and jitter constraints is returned (line 9).

Algorithm 2. Greedy algorithm.

INPUT: $P_r, W, E(r), \delta, v$
OUTPUT: $plan$

```

1:  $S \leftarrow [P_r]$ 
2: for  $p:1..P_r$  do
3:    $c_{best} \leftarrow \langle delay:\infty \rangle$ 
4:   for  $t: t(p)..(t(p) + \delta - totalTrxTime(E(r)))$  do
5:     if  $E(r)[0].\eta(t) = 0$  then continue
6:      $c \leftarrow findCandidateAllocation(p, t, W, E(r))$ 
7:     if  $c.delay < c_{best}.delay$  then  $c_{best} \leftarrow c$ 
8:     if  $c_{best}.delay > \delta$  then return INFEASIBLE
9:    $S[p] \leftarrow c_{best}$ 
10: return  $\langle schedule: S, jitter: computeJitter(S) \rangle$ 

```

Algorithm 3. findCandidateAllocation().

INPUT: $p, t, W, E(r)$
OUTPUT: candidate allocation

```

1:  $alloc \leftarrow [E(r)]; alloc[1] \leftarrow t$ 
2: for  $e: 1..|E(r)|-1$  do
3:    $t \leftarrow t * [E(r)[e-1].\tau / E(r)[e].\tau] + E(r)[e].\sigma$ 
4:    $found \leftarrow false$ 
5:   for  $t': t..2*|SF(e)|$  do
6:     if  $E(r)[0].\eta(t) = 1$  then
7:        $found \leftarrow true$ 
8:       break
9:   if NOT found then return  $\langle delay:\infty \rangle$ 
10:   $t \leftarrow t'; alloc[e] \leftarrow t$ 
11:  $d \leftarrow (E(r)[-1].\tau * alloc[-1] - E(r)[0].\tau * alloc[0])$ 
12: return  $\langle allocation: alloc, delay: d, period: p, first: t \rangle$ 

```

Algorithm 4. Local Search.

INPUT: $plan, \delta, v$
OUTPUT: $solution$

```

1: while  $plan.jitter > v$  do
2:    $c_{min}, c_{max} \leftarrow getMaxMinPeriodAlloc(plan.schedule)$ 
3:    $c \leftarrow findAlloc($ 
4:      $c_{min}.period, c_{min}.first, W, E(r), c_{max}.delay, \delta)$ 
5:    $plan_2 \leftarrow plan$ 
6:    $plan_2[c_{min}.period] \leftarrow c$ 
7:    $plan_2 \leftarrow computeJitter(plan_2)$ 
8:   if  $plan_2.jitter \geq plan.jitter$  then return INFEASIBLE
9:    $plan \leftarrow plan_2$ 
9: return  $plan$ 

```

V. NETWORK DIGITAL TWIN (NDT)

This section first introduces the proposed NDT to compute the KPIs of non-TS flows. Then, network partitioning and emulation is presented, which generates metrics that are afterwards used for KPIs computation.

A. NDT overview

As defined in the general provisioning algorithm in Fig. 4, a NDT is used to estimate the KPIs of requested and already deployed non-TS flows. To simplify KPI estimation, a *partition* of the complete network is defined, created as the union of the path(s) selected for the requested flow(s). The NDT emulates such network partition to estimate metrics and compute KPIs of requested and already established non-TS flows. The NDT considers the resources allocated to TS flows and propagates synthetically generated traffic targeting.

Network emulation entails the deployment of a scenario defined by means of a set of nodes and a set of links. Nodes consists of: *i*) input ports (*inport*) that receive traffic from other nodes; *ii*) output ports (*outport*) that forward traffic to other nodes; and *iii*) forwarding rules that map flows from inports to outports according to flow routes. Links connect an outport in one node to an inport in a neighboring node and include parameters such as transmission delay.

Three main types of nodes are considered, namely, *generators*, *switches*, and *sinks*. A *generator* is a type of node that produces

synthetic traffic for a flow in the form of arrays of bitrate values (in b/s). In the case of TS flows, traffic generation is based on the scheduling plan produced by the TS-FSP, so as to generate traffic only in the time intervals planned within each SF. As for the non-TS flows, traffic is generated according to probability distributions that characterize inter-arrival burst and packet time, and burst and packet size of the service mix characterizing the flow (see [14] for details). Traffic is generated with a pre-defined resolution κ . Generators have just one output that limits traffic generation to a maximum bitrate for traffic shaping purposes. On the other end, *Sink* nodes include a number of inports that serve as end points for each flow terminating at that node.

A *switch* is a node that represents a network device with flow switching capabilities (e.g., a WiFi AP or an Ethernet switch). Outputs in switch nodes implement the models and algorithms needed to accurately emulate the capabilities and performance of TS and non-TS capable interfaces. Specifically, time-aware *flow queue models*, based on the fluid flow model presented in [15], are used to emulate TS-capable interfaces following the general architecture in Fig. 3a. The queue model is defined as eq. (13), where $q(\cdot)$ is the queue state defined as the number of bytes in the buffer, $x(\cdot)$ is the actual input flow received, $y(\cdot)$ is the output flow leaving the queue, and $\mu(t)$ is the time-aware service rate.

$$\frac{d}{dt}(q(t)) = q'(t) = x(q(t), t) - y(q(t), \mu(t)) \quad (13)$$

In brief, network emulation consists in propagating traffic flows from generators to sinks, traversing switches. Such traffic propagation results in metrics, such as queued traffic in every queue of the outputs, that are afterwards used to compute per-flow KPIs, such as e2e delay. The NDT estimates two types of KPIs: *i) e2e KPIs*, which are provided for non-TS requests only; and *ii) KPIs variations* (Δ) computed on the network partition defined by the paths of the flows in the request, for the already deployed non-TS flows if the new flows were finally deployed.

In addition to the queue models and components, the NDT includes two databases (DB) that are conveniently updated during network operation: *i) the network DB* stores the current status of the network topology (active nodes and links), as well as the details of the already deployed flows; and *ii) a monitoring DB* with real e2e performance measurements (delay, throughput, and others) of the existing flows. It is worth mentioning that the availability of fine grain, segmented measurements is of paramount importance for the accuracy of KPI estimations produced by the NDT, as well as for QoS monitoring for service assurance guarantees. In this regard, techniques such as in-band network telemetry [25] can be adopted to obtain precise measurements with reduced impact on effective throughput and switching/routing performance.

Fig. 8: NDT main procedure.

Fig. 8 summarizes the main procedure executed by the NDT during an iteration of the provisioning process of a service request (see Fig. 4). The first step consists in computing the network partition (G') and selecting the existing flows (F') from the internal network DB (step 1 in Fig. 8). Then, traffic generators are built and configured to generate traffic according to the specifications in F' (including the requested flows) (2), and queues are configured to emulate the network partition G' (2'). The outputs of both processes are used to compose a set of *stages* concatenating generators, switches, and sinks (3). The propagation of the generated traffic through the stages (4) creates a set of metrics that, jointly with the available monitoring data of the existing flows, are used to estimate the KPIs (5) that are finally returned.

B. Network modelling and emulation

Fig. 9a shows an example of the network partition created in the NDT for evaluating the provisioning request of TS-2 in the example in Fig. 2. In this example, all established flows share, at least, one interface with the request, so all of them are included in the emulation. However, those links that are not in the path of TS-2 are excluded from the partition, e.g., links AP2-SW1 and R1-SW1.

Fig. 9: Example of network partition (a) and detail of SW1 (b).

Algorithm 5. Node Propagation.

INPUT: S, i, j
OUTPUT: S

```

1: if  $S(i, j).type = \text{"generator"}$  then
2:    $y \leftarrow \text{generate}(S(i, j))$ 
3:    $p \leftarrow S(i, j).outPort$ 
4:    $S(i', j', p') \leftarrow \text{get\_neighbor}(S(i, j, p))$ 
5:    $\text{add\_input\_traffic}(S(i', j', p'), y)$ 
6: else if  $S(i, j).type = \text{"switch"}$  then
7:    $X_{TS}, X_{non-TS} \leftarrow \text{split\_input\_traffic}(S(i, j))$ 
8:   for  $p$  in  $S(i, j).outPorts$  do
9:      $X'_{TS}, X'_{non-TS} \leftarrow \text{in\_out\_mapping}(X_{TS}, X_{non-TS}, p)$ 
10:     $p.\mu \leftarrow \text{reserve\_time\_slots}(X'_{TS})$ 
11:    for  $pr: 0..7$  do
12:       $x \leftarrow \text{select\_priority}(X'_{TS}, pr)$ 
13:       $y \leftarrow \text{propagate}(p, x)$  (eq. (13))
14:       $\langle i', j', p' \rangle \leftarrow \text{get\_neighbor}(S(i, j, p))$ 
15:       $\text{add\_input\_traffic}(S(i', j', p'), y)$ 
16:       $p.\mu \leftarrow \text{update}(p.\mu, y)$  (eq. (14))
17: return  $S$ 

```

The figure also shows the different stages that are defined and concatenated to propagate the traffic flows from generators to sinks. Let S be the set of stages, $S(i, j)$ be node j in stage i , and $S(i, j, p)$ be port p (import or export) in $S(i, j)$. The connection between nodes in two consecutive stages is performed at the port level if they are connected by a link in the network, e.g., ports $S(i, j, p)$ with $S(i+1, j', p')$. Note that nodes in each stage can be independently evaluated, which enables parallel execution.

Algorithm 5 shows the process to propagate flows through a given node. It receives the set of stages and the index of a particular node to evaluate and returns the set S updated with metrics such as queued traffic in the outports. The algorithm executes different actions if the node is a generator (lines 1-5 in Algorithm 5) or a switch (lines 6-16), while no propagation is performed in case of a sink node.

In case of a generator, synthetic traffic (represented by vector y) is produced with m values generated with the pre-configured resolution κ (line 2), where κ is represented by the duration τ_e of each time slot in the link in the network partition and m equals the number of slots in the related SF _{e} (line 2). Note that τ_e is limited by the precision of clock synchronization. The traffic is then injected into the neighbor import (lines 3-5) ready to be processed in the next stage.

Algorithm 6. KPIs computation.

INPUT: S, DB
OUTPUT: KPI

```

1:  $F_{non-TS} \leftarrow \text{get\_nonTS\_flows}(S)$ 
2:  $KPI \leftarrow \{\}$ 
3: for  $f$  in  $F_{non-TS}$  do
4:    $d \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
5:   for  $S(i, j, p)$  in  $\text{get\_path}(S, f)$  do
6:      $d \leftarrow d + S(i, j, p).d_e + S(i, j, p).d_q$  (eqs. (15)-(17))
7:     if  $S(i, j).type = \text{"sink"}$  then  $thr \leftarrow S(i, j, p).x$ 
8:     if  $f.eval\_type = \text{"inc"}$  then  $d \leftarrow d - \text{get\_delay}(DB, f)$ 
9:      $KPI[f][\text{"delay"}] \leftarrow \{\text{"avg": avg}(d), \text{"max": max}(d)\}$ 
10:     $KPI[f][\text{"thruput"}] \leftarrow \{\text{"avg": avg}(thr), \text{"max": max}(thr)\}$ 
11: return  $KPI$ 

```

In case of a switch, the traffic of the flows entering the node is separated into TS and non-TS (line 7). Then, the following steps are performed for every output (lines 8-16): *i*) the subset of input traffic flows mapped to that output is selected (line 9); *ii*) the entire capacity of the port (i.e., service rate μ) is reserved at the beginning of the SF with a duration of the aggregated time windows allocated to TS flows (line 10). $\mu(t)$ is a vector of length m and μ_{max} is defined as the nominal bitrate of the port; and *iii*) non-TS flows are sequentially processed in decreasing priority (lines 11-16). Given a priority pr , the aggregated traffic x belonging to such priority is selected and propagated through the queue according to the fluid flow model presented in eq. (13) (lines 12-13). The resultant traffic y is added to the neighboring port (lines 14-15). Before processing traffic of the next priority, μ is updated by subtracting the capacity y used by the current priority (eq. (14)) (line 16) and the updated set of stages is returned (line 17).

$$\mu(t) = \max(0, \mu(t) - y(t)), \forall t = 1..m \quad (14)$$

Fig. 9b illustrates the node propagation process for the traffic flows propagated through node SW1. Flows are received through 3 different inports and are forwarded to a common output; the details of the propagation are shown as an inset in Fig. 9b: *i*) x_{TS-1} and x_{TS-2} reserve a time window of enough duration at the starting of the SF interval; *ii*) the remaining capacity is then used to serve traffic flows x_{QoS-1} and x_{QoS-2} because of their higher priority; and *iii*) the output of the higher priority flows is used to reduce the service rate that remain available for serving low-priority traffic flow x_{BE} .

C. KPI computation

The result of the node propagation process through the stages and nodes generates metrics that are stored in S . Among the different metrics, we consider the following ones for every stage and node, and for every time $t=1..m$:

- the traffic $x(t)$ received per flow at every inport and the traffic $y(t)$ sent per flow through every output.
- the constant transmission delay d_e collected at every inport.
- the queueing delay $d_q(t)$ caused by traffic buffering at every output that depends on the service rate among others.

The proposed NDT is based on flow propagation and, therefore, no per-packet metrics are available. To overcome this issue, we propose eq. (15) to estimate d_q as the sum of two time-components: *i*) t_w represents the waiting time due to service rate reservation for TS flows and computed as eq. (16), where function $next$ returns the next time to t where service rate is non-zero; and *ii*) t_q is the estimated time to empty the current buffer $q(t)$ at service rate $\mu(t)$, computed as eq. (17). For the sake of simplicity, we assume that the queue is emptied at the speed of the current service rate when the latter is non-zero and at a constant average value μ_{avg} computed for the whole emulated time when the current service rate is zero.

$$d_q(t) = t_w(\mu(t)) + t_q(q(t), \mu(t)) \quad \forall t = 1..m \quad (15)$$

$$t_w(\mu(t)) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } \mu(t) > 0 \\ t' - t & \text{if } \mu(t) = 0, t' = next(\mu(t') > 0) \end{cases} \quad (16)$$

$$t_q(q(t), \mu(t)) = \begin{cases} 8 \cdot \frac{q(t)}{\mu(t)} & \text{if } \mu(t) > 0 \\ 8 \cdot \frac{q(t)}{\mu_{avg}} & \text{if } \mu(t) = 0 \end{cases} \quad (17)$$

Algorithm 6 presents the pseudocode of the algorithm to compute e2e and *incremental* KPIs. It starts by selecting the non-TS flows and initializing the KPIs to return (lines 1-2 in Algorithm 6). Then, the path of each flow is retrieved and the e2e delay d is computed as the sum of d_e and d_q components, element-wise for every time t , for all the ports in the path (lines 3-6). When reaching its sink node, flow input traffic is stored as throughput (*thruput*) (line 7). In case of incremental evaluation, the delay monitored in the segments of the evaluated path is retrieved from the monitoring DB and used to recompute the estimated e2e delay as the variation w.r.t. the monitored one (line 8). Finally, the KPIs (delay and throughput) for every flow are stored (lines 9-10). Note that the aforementioned process generates values for every time t reproduced in the emulation. To facilitate performance evaluation analysis and further decision making, the detailed values are summarized in average and maximum statistics and returned as KPIs (line 11).

VI. RESULTS

In this section, we evaluate the performance of the provisioning algorithm for TS and non-TS flows proposed in Section III, together with the solutions in Sections IV and V.

Fig. 10: Network topology for evaluation purposes.

For the performance evaluation, we consider the network topology in Fig. 10, which is in line with Fig. 2 introduced in Section III. Four customer networks are connected through three packet nodes belonging to a transport network; we assume that a network slice is used to support such connection and provide the required isolation [27]. The duration of the SF T was set to 10ms. From the flows that can be requested on the topology, we focus on those connecting: *i*) devices in the factory networks A and B (TS flows); *ii*) factory network A and datacenter, for device control purposes (TS flows) and data (e.g., video) processing (non-TS flows), and *iii*) traffic (non-TS flows) between area A and the datacenter.

The rest of the section focuses on the evaluation of TS and non-TS flow provisioning. The provisioning of TS flows is firstly faced and the performance of the ILP and heuristic approach for solving the TS-FSP problem are compared on a set of small instances. Once validated, the heuristic approach is used for solving real-sized problem instances. Finally, the provisioning of non-TS flows is faced and the NDT is used to predict how the performance of those flows will be impacted. All components have been implemented in Python 3.1, and experiments were executed in an Intel Core i7 12th Gen with 64GB RAM running Ubuntu 22.04.

A. Performance of the TS-FSP solvers

Let us analyze the performance of the methods for solving the TS-FSP problem proposed in Section IV, aiming to confirm the anticipated long solving times of the ILP formulation in Section IV.C and validating the heuristic approach proposed in Section IV.D.

Recall that the size of ILP problem instances is related to the speed of the network interfaces, i.e., to the considered time slot granularity τ_e . In consequence, we generated different problem instances of increased size considering network interfaces in the range [10, 100] Mb/s for all the nodes in Fig. 10 (assuming a single AP per factory network) and compare the quality of the solutions and the solving times of the ILP and the heuristic. 50 requests between factory networks A and B were generated that arrived sequentially with the following configuration $(P, \delta, v, b) = (10\text{ms}, 10\text{ms}, 1\text{ms}, \text{random } [80, 120] \text{ bytes})$.

Fig. 11 shows the obtained results aggregated for all the requests for the obtained e2e delay (Fig. 11a) and jitter (Fig. 11b). We observe that in all the cases, the requests were served with delay and jitter under the required maximum, which validates the quality of the solutions obtained by the heuristic algorithm. However, the solving time of the ILP (Fig. 11c) shows a clear increment with the size of the problem, which is as high as 25s when the speed of the interfaces increases to 80 Mb/s. This is in contrast to the really fast heuristic execution that takes under 0.5 s to produce near-optimal solutions. These results confirm the analysis in Section IV.C and validate the proposed heuristic approach and therefore, we rely on such approach for the rest of the performance evaluation.

Fig. 11: Performance comparison of TS-FSP solving methods.

Fig. 12: Performance TS flows for several TS flow requests scenarios.

Fig. 13: Performance TS flows for several TS flow requests scenarios under zero queuing delay scheduling [10].

B. Provisioning TS flows

We now move to a scenario where wired links are based on 10 Gb/s optical interfaces with $\tau_e=0.8\text{ns}$ and $b_e=1$ byte. Links connecting the switches in the transport network accumulate a transmission delay of $300\ \mu\text{s}$. The rest of wired links are short distance and have negligible delay. MCS-5 is used for WiFi interfaces, which entails $\tau_e=0.5\ \mu\text{s}$, $b_e=3$ bytes and propagation delay $4\ \mu\text{s}$. We assume that TS flows are requested by two applications requiring deterministic communications. Table 3 provides the details of the flows for each application, which are in line with the AGV use case presented in [11].

Table 3: Characteristics of TSN flows for the considered applications.

<i>Param</i>	<i>TSN Application-1</i>	<i>TSN Application-2</i>
P	1 ms	10 ms
δ	1 ms	10 ms
v	100 μs	1 ms
b	random [90, 120] bytes	random [900, 1200] bytes

We have developed a simulator that follow the provisioning algorithm described in Section III. The simulator generates single-flow service requests for a randomly selected TSN application and involving devices/servers from the customer networks. The requests arrive sequentially and if a request is accepted, the selected resources are reserved and the simulator continues with the next request, which is processed on the resources remaining available on the network.

Fig. 12 presents the obtained e2e delay (upper row) and jitter (lower row) for the requested TS flows; evolution of the maximum and mean values is presented separately for each application. Fig. 12a shows the results for requests between devices in factory network A and B (FN2FN) and the store&forward mode is considered, whereas Fig. 12b presents the results when the express mode is considered. In both cases, we observe that delay and jitter increase with the number of flows in the network (load), being the maximum delay and jitter under the required ones. Because of the characteristics of the network topology and the applications, we stop the simulation when a request cannot be served, as no more requests will be accepted. It is worth noting that the delay of flows for application 2 have zero jitter, since the period of those flows and the duration of the SF coincide. In general, we observe very little difference in the performance of both modes. Fig. 12c-d present the results for a mixed number of requests between devices in factory network A and the datacenter (FN2DC) for a mix of requests from both applications. In this case, we observe a clear reduction in the e2e delay of flows from application 2 that benefits from the wired interfaces in the datacenter in contrast to the WiFi network in the previous scenario. As in the previous case, we observe very little difference in the performance of both modes.

To quantify the benefits of the assumed per-TS queue in the output interfaces of the time-aware switches, we reproduced the previous scenario for the zero queuing delay model. The results are presented in Fig. 13, where we observe that only part of the TS flow requests can be served, resulting in blocking as high as approximately 40% in store-and-forward mode and around 30% in express mode. Additionally, the delay experienced by the served applications increases rapidly with the number of requests.

The previous results were obtained for the finest possible granularity, for which the allocated size of the time windows provides the exact capacity required by the service requests.

Fig. 14: Increment of capacity vs granularity.

However, it is not clear whether such fine granularity can be supported in practice due to the precision of the synchronization in the case of high-speed (Gb/s) interfaces. In consequence, let us study the extra capacity that would be needed when the considered granularity is coarser (based on a multiplier g). Fig. 14 presents the obtained results, where we observe that the effect of g is almost linear to the extra capacity required. Even when g is as coarse as 100 (i.e., τ_e/b_e equal 80ns/100bytes for 10Gb/s interfaces and 50 μ s/300bytes for WiFi interfaces), the extra capacity is under 10%. However, such granularity is still close to the precision of PTPv2, which clearly motivates the development of more accurate protocols for synchronization in the case that higher-speed interfaces are used to support TSN traffic.

C. KPIs estimation of non-TS flows

Let us now evaluate the accuracy of KPI estimation of non-TS flows, in particular the estimation of the queueing delay, which is based on combining the time-aware flow queue models in Section V.B and the equations (15)-(17) in Section V.C (hereafter referred to as *flow-based*). A discrete event-based simulator that emulates the behavior of IEEE 802.1Qbv compliant interfaces packet-by-packet (hereafter referred to as *packet-based*) is used for benchmarking purposes.

We consider the network topology in Fig. 10 with 10 WiFi APs in each factory floor assuming that the speed of wired links is: *i*) 1 Gb/s for links between APs and transport network switches, e.g., link AP-A1->SW1; and *ii*) 10 Gb/s for links between transport network switches; e.g., link SW1-SW2. Packet-based traffic generators have been implemented to generate synthetic packet traces with different mixes of TS and non-TS traffic flows. The traffic of non-TS flows is defined in terms of burst size, inter-burst time and inter-packet time according to the characteristics in [13] with fixed packet size equal to 1400 bytes. The generated packets are directly processed by the packet-based simulator, whereas packet traces are aggregated in flows of resolution κ before being processed by the flow-based method. Multiple flows with different characteristics are combined to generate a traffic mix defined in terms of total non-TS traffic bitrate.

We denote ρ_{TS} as the load of TS traffic, defined as the percentage of time that the SF is occupied by established TS flows. We run a set of simulations considering $\rho_{TS} = \{25\%, 50\%\}$ and non-TS traffic ranging 0.1-0.6 Gb/s for the 1Gb/s links assuming a typical periodic daily pattern [13]. To allow accurate and efficient KPI estimation assuming daily periodicity of the traffic, we performed one execution of 10 seconds of simulation time for each day hour, for both packet-based and flow-based approaches. Recall that, in the case of the flow-based approach, the number of traffic values m generated synthetically depends on the pre-

configured resolution κ . In this regard, we consider a wide range of κ values, from fine ($\kappa = 50 \mu\text{s}$) to coarse ($\kappa = 10 \text{ms}$, i.e., the considered SF duration) resolution.

Fig. 15: Error of delay estimation for 1Gb/s (a) and 10Gb/s (b) links; example of link delay performance (c).

Fig. 16: Reduction of execution time.

Fig. 17: Established flows and request under evaluation.

Fig. 18: Incremental delay example.

Table 4: Comparative of Execution Time (sec).

Exhaustive Simulation				Short periods			
1 Gb/s		10 Gb/s		1 Gb/s		10 Gb/s	
Packet	Flow	Packet	Flow	Packet	Flow	Packet	Flow
4,082	158	64,080	171	11.34	0.44	178	0.476

Fig. 15a-b show the average and maximum relative error of flow-based queueing delay estimation compared to that of the packet-based simulator, for 1Gb/s and 10Gb/s links, respectively as a function of the resolution. We observe that mean and maximum error of the flow-based method is under 12% and 25%, respectively for both 1Gb/s and 10Gb/s links for fine and moderated resolution, e.g., for $\kappa = 100 \mu\text{s}$, and increases exponentially for coarser resolutions. In order to better visualize the accuracy of the flow-based method, Fig. 15c shows the delay estimated by both methods for the case of a 1Gb/s link and $\kappa = 100 \mu\text{s}$. The curves show the estimated delay for TS traffic configurations $\rho_{TS} = \{25\%, 50\%, 75\%\}$, as a function of the non-TS traffic. It is worth mentioning that the small observed error is in line with the percentages shown in Fig. 15a. Particularly, we observe that the flow-based method slight over-estimates the delay, which is, in fact, beneficial for KPIs estimation purposes, as it introduces an additional margin towards safer and more conservative decision making.

Let us now focus on the analysis of execution time. Fig. 16 compares the running time of the flow-based method w.r.t. that of the packet-based simulator as a function of the resolution. We observe that the flow-based method runs faster than the packet-based simulator. Specifically, for a moderated resolution $\kappa = 100 \mu\text{s}$, the flow-based method runs 33 (219) times faster than the packet-based simulator in the case of 1 Gb/s (10 Gb/s) links. The difference is due to the fact that the execution time of the flow-based method depends of the resolution regardless of the traffic volume, whereas packet-based simulator execution time depends on the number of packets to process, which remarkably increases with larger traffic volumes. Table 4 reports absolute execution times for both approaches and 1 and 10Gb/s link speeds for load $\rho_{TS} = 25\%$ and $\kappa = 100 \mu\text{s}$ for the flow-based method. We observe that building an NDT for KPI computation based on exhaustive simulation is not scalable and it does not meet the execution time constraints for flow provisioning, even using the flow-based approach. In view of these results, we propose to evaluate short periods, e.g., 10 seconds, at every day hour as a way to provide accurate KPI computation, while reducing computation times. Table 4 reports the obtained results for this approach, where we observe the large reduction in the execution time for both packet-based simulator and flow-based method. However, the former still require long execution times for 10Gb/s links, whereas the flow-based method provides sub-second execution time for both link speeds.

Once the performance of the flow-based method has been validated, let us focus on illustrating the application of Algorithm 6, specifically on computing the incremental delay of the existing non-TS flows upon the provisioning of a new flow request. Fig. 17 reproduces the topology in Fig. 10 for a case where a set of TS and non-TS flows are already established, and request r

needs to be evaluated. Note that Algorithm 6 will return the incremental KPIs of f_{QoS} (priority 4) and f_{BE} (priority 1) because the paths for those flows intercept only partially that of the request. We assume a typical daily traffic pattern [13] ranging 100-600 Mb/s for both flows. In addition, several TSN flows, collectively labeled f_{TSN} , represent a load $\rho_{TS} = 25\%$ on the transport network. We consider two different cases for the request: *i*) r is a new non-TS flow that would follow a similar traffic pattern than f_{QoS} with priority 2; and *ii*) r is a new TS flow that would increase load ρ_{TS} to 30%. Fig. 18 shows the maximum delay computed by Algorithm 6 for the non-TS flows in both cases. When r is a non-TS flow, the delay increment is moderated (even zero) on the evaluated segment. Note that although the incremental delay of f_{BE} increases, that of the f_{QoS} remains unchanged due to the different priorities of the flows. Anyway, the delay increment of f_{BE} would be only marginal. In the case when the request is TS, however, the increment of delay increases dramatically for all the non-TS flows, especially for f_{BE} with delay increment of up to 0.5ms, due to the reduction of available time slots within the SF.

VII. CONCLUDING REMARKS

A complete solution for the provisioning of TS and non-TS flows have been proposed in this paper. A general algorithm for flow provisioning running in the control plane was presented that involves: *i*) a TS FSP to plan TS flow time windows across a defined path; and *ii*) an NDT to evaluate the KPIs on non-TS flows. The TS-FSP problem was formally stated as an optimization problem, and modeled as an ILP. A heuristic approach was proposed to provide near-optimal solutions in short time. The NDT was based on the CURSA-SQ methodology and emulates a network partitioning with the nodes and links in the paths of the flows. A queue system reproducing such network partitioning is solved in practical times to generate metrics used for KPIs computation.

An illustrative network scenario was used to showcase the operation of the TS FSP and the NDT upon service requests arrivals. The performance evaluation of the methods for solving the TS-FSP problem confirmed the long solving times of the ILP formulation and validated the heuristic approach. Two forwarding modes were studied aimed at reducing the delay of TS flows: the traditional store&forward and the express mode. The results showed little difference in the performance of both modes. Different granularities, defined in terms of time slot width were analyzed, since it is not clear whether the finest possible granularity can be supported in practice due to the precision of the synchronization in the case of Gb/s interfaces. The results showed that a granularity multiplier of 100 results in extra capacity of about 10%, i.e., 1Gb/s in 10Gb/s interfaces. However, such granularity is still close to the precision of PTPv2, so the granularity must be coarser for 100Gb/s interfaces. This motivates the development and adoption of more accurate protocols for synchronization.

The accuracy of the estimation of the queueing delay, which is key for the KPI estimation of non-TS flows, was afterwards evaluated. The results showed the high accuracy of the proposed flow-based method, based on time-aware flow queue models, as compared to a packet-based simulator, running the former much faster than the latter. In conclusion, the proposed flow-based method produces accurate, sub-second KPI estimation in an efficient way in heterogeneous scenarios mixing TS and non-TS traffic flows.

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